

Tools4CAP FIRST INFO SESSION

HIGHLIGHTS REPORT

26 June 2023

The first [Tools4CAP](#) (Innovative Toolbox empowering effective CAP governance towards EU ambitions) [info session](#) took place on 26 June 2023. The event gathered over 110 attendees from different backgrounds.

Tools4CAP wants to promote [meaningful engagement](#) stakeholders that may benefit from this project. This first info session aimed at (i) presenting the project; (ii) informing about the first outcomes and possibilities to be involved; (iii) explaining the Tools4CAP Academy; and (iv) enhance the exchange and learning.

During the info session, four presentations were made by [Ecorys](#) as project coordinator and [AEIDL](#). They addressed the following points:

- Presentation of the project and its usefulness for the improvement of the design and monitoring of the national Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plans (CAP SPs).
- Progress on the inventory of existing methods and tools.
- Overview of all the activities in which external actors can [get involved](#).
- Explanation of the objectives and the nearby development of the [Tools4CAP Academy](#).

The event featured other three presentations on:

- Horizon Europe programme: Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal, provided by **Celine Choquer** from the European Commission Research Executive Agency;
- [ScaleAgdata](#): **Laurent Tits** (VITO), the project coordinator of this sister project explained the potential that lies in opening the data from in-situ sensors on farms for a European-wide monitoring of agri-environmental conditions; and
- The new features of the the current CAP programming period (2023-2027), the design of the Strategic Plans and lessons for the future, presented by **Marina Brakalova**, policy officer at the European Commission Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI).

The info session, facilitated by **Serafin Pazos-Vidal** (AEIDL) concluded with a series of next steps including that the meeting materials and the report on the main elements discussed will be available on the [event page](#) and the first [newsletter](#). Work has already started in the preparation of the first module of the Tools4CAP Academy. It will take place in November 2023 (date to be confirmed) and will focus on the inventory.

ORGANISER:

26 JUNE 2023

ONLINE

110 PARTICIPANTS
(EU institutions, public authorities, research, innovators, farmers, other EU-funded projects, etc.)

22 COUNTRIES

PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

If you see this icon, click to see the presentation

If you see this icon, click to see the video

TOOLS4CAP IN A NUTSHELL

The Tools4CAP project

Bérénice Dupeux

Tools4CAP project coordinator, Ecorys

Bérénice Dupeux (Ecorys) presented the [Tools4CAP](#) project, the new developments in the CAP 2023-2027 to which it is responding (including integration of Pillar I and II, focusing on results and a new delivery model), and its usefulness for the improvement of the design and monitoring of the national CAP SPs. She pointed out that greater subsidiarity includes more challenges and specificities in each of the CAP Strategic Plans.

Tools4CAP is a Coordination and Support Action in Horizon Europe (2023-2026) coordinated by [Ecorys](#), gathering 20 [partner organisations](#), that aims to support the design and monitoring of the current national CAP SPs and lay the foundations for sound preparation of post-2027 Strategic Plans through a bottom-up adaptation of innovative methods and tools. She expressed that the project aims to bridge the gap between science and policy as well as to foster long-term planning.

The project will provide ready-to-use quantitative and qualitative solutions, including modelling tools with foresight capacity, participatory and multi-governance decision tools, and new data and monitoring solutions.

Tools4CAP has among its key actions delivering a comprehensive inventory of methods and tools used in the 27 Member States, methodological guidelines on innovative solutions and a handbook of good practices. Furthermore, it will establish a Replication Lab to demonstrate the use of innovative methods and tools in 10 Member States through [case studies](#).

This initial work will then feed the three Tools4CAP work streams (innovative, tools, participatory decision-making and novel data). In turn they will feed the Replication Lab. Tools4CAP is not a traditional research project, hence will not develop new tools, methodologies or technologies but instead will focus on developing innovative approaches in CAP delivery by supporting and improving cooperation between EU countries, education and knowledge sharing, public awareness and transparency, collaboration with the scientific community and long-term planning.

Bérénice on the key asset of Tools4CAP: *"We are creating the best knowledge available. If you are facing problems in developing, for example, an ecosystem, you can consult our results and access the best information"*.

Tools4CAP key outcomes

FEATURED SPEAKERS

Horizon Europe programme: Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal

Celine Choquer

REA European Commission

Celine Choquer from the European Commission Research Executive Agency (REA) introduced the work and support provided by REA in supporting the EU Research and Innovation policy and the structure and intervention logic of the Horizon Europe Programme. Horizon Europe is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation until 2027 with a budget of €95.5 billion.

The aim of the strategic plan is to ensure an effective interface between EU policy priorities, and programme activities and ultimately, the research and innovation projects funded by Horizon Europe. Each of the key strategic orientations are translated in expected impacts are structured by clusters.

Furthermore, the strategic plan identifies European co-programmed and co-funded partnerships, as well as the EU missions. DG AGRI is working in the new Strategic Plan 2025-2027.

Within Horizon Pillar II on Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness, the cluster on Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment expect to generate impact on innovative governance models enabling sustainability, environmental observation.

She also presented the main features, priorities and projects of the Call on innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal. Projects in this segment include the following: LAMASUS, Land Support, Bright Space, Agricore, MIND STEP, BESTMAP, BATModel, MATS, Trade.

The following question was posed to the speaker: among the sister projects that were selected, what is the common element of these projects? What is their common added value? *Celine answered that they share a maximum degree on 3 criteria (excellence, impact and implementation). Also, their multi-actor approach and a rich co-creation process.*

Support is currently being provided to 41 thematic networks and 2 ongoing advisory networks that strengthen advise on enhancing consumer-producer relations –CORENET and EU4Advice. Others are in the pipeline. Projects like modernAKIS are also contributing to the development of more efficient and effective agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS). Check the [factsheet](#).

Finally, she advanced the key aspects of the European Commission's call for proposals in 2024. Check [here](#) the information days.

ScaleAgdata Horizon Europe project

Laurent Tits

VITO (project coordinator of ScaleAgdata)

Laurent Tits, the project coordinator of [ScaleAgdata](#) (2023-2026), explained the potential that lies in opening the data from in-situ sensors on farms for a European-wide monitoring of agri-environmental conditions.

ScaleAgdata (Scaling Agricultural Sensor Data for an improved monitoring of agri-environmental conditions) is a Horizon Europe project (2023-2026) with 26 partners and includes 6 Labs (a. water productivity, b. crop management, c. yield monitoring, d. soil health, e. grasslands and f. sustain dairy). Its vision includes two pillars:

- Making the data available: obtain insights in how the complex data streams should be governed and organised.
- Making optimal use of the data: develop the data technology needed to scale data collected at the farm level to regional datasets agri-environmental monitoring and the management of agricultural production.

The project seeks to upscale skills and diversify the studies through variation of geography, crops and sector maturity.

He explained the different innovation areas covered in the project and their interconnectedness. These areas include innovative sensor technology, edge processing, data sharing architecture, data governance, satellite data augmentation, data assimilation, service development, privacy-preserving technology, and data integration methodologies.

Among the main elements of innovation in the purpose of the, Laurent pointed out that farmers are using more and more data, and there a huge potential in using this data. It is challenging to have access to this data. So, the project aims at marking data available and usable.

The speaker responded to the question of how the project contributes to reducing technological inequality. Laurent spoke about the availability and accessibility of data: *"When data is available, how do we help farmers who do not have access to it? This is a very specific component of the project. Our aim is to facilitate access for farmers, taking into account their initial economic situation, skills and knowledge"*.

FEATURED SPEAKERS

Novelties in the CAP 2023-2027, the design of the Strategic Plans and lessons for the future

Marina Brakalova

DG AGRI European Commission

Marina Brakalova, policy officer at the European Commission Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI) presented the new features of the current CAP programming period 2023-2027, the design of the CAP Strategic Plans in the Member States and lessons learned for the future.

She started presenting the key elements of the CAP reform and the introduction of the national CAP Strategic Plans. This is the first time there are a holistic integrated plan for all CAP interventions in each Member State. In the preparation of the national Strategic Plans, the European Commission provided a total of 402 recommendations to the Member States related to economy/markets, environment/climate, social/health, knowledge and innovation. The recommendations accompanied the process of preparing the plans through a SWOT analysis, the identification and prioritisation of needs, the selection of interventions and the financial allocation and setting of targets for results indicators. Observation letters to Member States and the Plans can be found on the EC [website](#).

The Commission prioritised the following in the Strategic Plans:

- Strengthened structured dialogue between Member States and Commission.
- Provision of training and tools to Member States and reinforce the partnership principle.

In particular, the Commission urged Member States to involve competent authorities for the environment and climate provisions of the Plans, and reinforce the partnership principle, involving in the preparation and delivery of the plans:

- All relevant public bodies (including competent regional and local authorities).
- Economic and social partners.
- Relevant bodies representing civil society.

The challenges identified by the Commission throughout this process were: time pressure, target setting, linking of the budget to targets, balancing competing objectives, the need for complementarity between many tools, the necessity of understanding the outputs for what this limited funding in a limited period.

Finally, Marina concluded that *"Tools4CAP is an important project for the Commission, as we are in a new planning process. It is crucial to keep learning and sharing between Member States. Communication is crucial for avoiding reluctance to change of farmers, as well as monitoring. Further learning and sharing of good practices between Member States is crucial. Communication, outreach and awareness-raising are essential. In addition, there must be ongoing monitoring, measurement and evaluation"*.

Towards a performance-oriented CAP

TOOLS4CAP FIRST ACTIVITIES

Inventory of methods and tools used by Member States

Bérénice Dupeux

Tools4CAP project coordinator, Ecorys

Bérénice Dupeux (Ecorys) introduced the inventory of existing methods and tools, which will be one of the first results of Tools4CAP. It will include methods and tools used for the design, implementation and monitoring of Strategic Plans, as well as those used in previous programming periods. Relevant stakeholders at local, national and European level in the 27 Member States are being interviewed for the open-access inventory, while launching is expected for September. The main milestones are:

- Policy analysis tools for ex-ante evidence-based decisions: e.g. Simulation tools, scenario analysis, impact assessment, etc.
- Policy choices supporting tools: e.g. Logic models and theory of change, coherence matrix, multi-criteria decision and planning tools, etc.
- Monitoring tools for data and knowledge stocktaking: e.g. Database integration interface, social media analytics, AI data interpretation tools, precision farming data tools, etc.

The inventory classification system shall include:

She presented examples of the four preliminary methodological areas in which methods and tools will be classified:

- One of the four methodological areas;
- The objectives (needs assessment and intervention logic);
- The evaluation criteria: Applicability-Efficiency-Transparency;
- Examples.

- Participatory and multi-stakeholder tools: e.g. Cumulative voting, stakeholder consultations, focus and working expert groups, etc.

Bérénice concluded that *"all tools are in constant development, as policy framework is also changing. Tools4CAP wants to reflect on the tools to foster the debate and the improvement of the Plans"*.

Engagement with stakeholders and the Tools4CAP Academy

Blanca Casares

Policy expert and project manager (AEIDL)

Blanca Casares (AEIDL), who is responsible for Tools4CAP Capacity Building Hub, explained how Tools4CAP foresees the [active participation](#) from external stakeholders and the use of project' results.

By the end of 2023 there will be a better understanding of the CAP new delivery model, by the end of 2024 there will be knowledge on how to adapt the existing tools, and in the years 2025 and 2026 updates, replication, and proposal of case studies for the CAP after 2027. This is particularly timely as this work will coincide with the preparation by the Commission of the post 2027 CAP.

Tools4CAP ambitions to promote meaningful engagement of external actors go well beyond sharing results. The project seeks to involve policy-makers at European, national and regional level and governance bodies, but also researchers, innovators and developers and other relevant actors of agriculture and rural development.

The project provides the possibility to get involved in different activities: focus groups, interviews, surveys, training sessions and dissemination activities. The [consent form](#) is available at the website.

TOOLS4CAP FIRST ACTIVITIES

Blanca also outlined the main elements of the Tools4CAP Capacity Building Hub. It will help users to reinforce their capacity for using innovative tools. It will rely on a [Stakeholder Engagement Platform](#) and the [Tools4CAP Academy](#).

The Tools4CAP Academy, coordinated by [AEIDL](#) in close collaboration with other project partners, will organise a series of EU-level workshops, to disseminate, showcase, and train end users in how to best choose and operationalise innovative solutions and good practices.

She also presented the planned activities to provide a framework for capacity building and peer-learning in order to develop an attractive and tailored training programme composed of 10 modules to meet the end-users' needs. The results will be consolidated into a Capacity Building Toolkit, which will be translated into 16 languages.

The preparation of the first module of the Tools4CAP Academy is going to start. It will take place in November 2023 (date to be confirmed) and will deal with the inventory.

In the first half of 2024, two ad hoc modules will be organised according to the needs of the end users of the project. The prospective participants have already been were on the most relevant topics that will be covered are as follows:

- Indicators for CAP evaluation (23.3% of participants)
- Data management and result-based intervention (23.3% of participants)
- Governance process and stakeholder engagement (18.6% of participants)
- Intervention logic (11.6% of participants)
- Effective preparation for CAP SP design (9.3% of participants)
- Assessing the internal and external coherence of CAP interventions (7% of participants)
- Data collection (7% of participants)

A number of other topics have also been proposed: regional dimension of the CAP Strategic Plans, governance of amendments, digital tools and planning process and project management for CAP Strategic Plans Managing Authorities and the European Commission.

The following modules will be organised over the next three years: three modules linked to the identification of tools, methodological guidelines and technical protocols on data integration (between October 2024 and June 2025), one module showcasing case study set-up plans (around October 2025), two modules showcasing case study analysis and descriptive factsheets (first semester 2026) and one module on the Handbook of good practices in cases studies (second semester 2026). The information and materials of the modules will be available in the [specific section](#) of the website.

In closing the event Serafin Pazos-Vidal (AEIDL) thanked the large audience and reminded recordings, presentations and this Highlights report will be available in the coming days. Preparation of first module of the Tools4CAP Academy will start and will take place in November 2023. (a) the conceptual and analytical framework; (b) the inventory of methods and tools and (c) the first round of focus groups within the [Stakeholder Engagement Platform](#).

All presentations and recordings are available at the [event page](#).

Get involved in the project, [here](#).

Or sign up for the newsletter, [here](#).

www.tools4cap.eu

